

Impact of Social Network Application on Interest and Performance in Concept Quadratic Equation among Secondary Students in Yenagoa Metropolis

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of social network application on interest and performance in concept quadratic equation among secondary students in Yenagoa metropolis. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The instrument used for data collection was Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The instrument was validated by two experts in Mathematics and Measurement and evaluation and its reliability coefficient was found to be 0.87 using Kuder Richardson formula 20. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was adopted in testing the hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ level of significance. The two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that there was significant difference in the mathematics interest and performance of students taught using Slack and those taught using without social networking teaching app. Also, there was significant difference in the mathematics interest and performance of students taught using WhatsApp and those taught using without social networking teaching app. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that mathematics teachers should be encouraged to use social networking tools in teaching/learning of mathematics to help the students gain experiences on the strategy in order to enhance high performance level amongst them.

Keywords: Interest, Achievement, Social Network Application Tools

Introduction

Mathematics is a science that deal with the logic of shapes, quantity and arrangement. It is a discipline that is found to be more related to the scientific and technological facets of man's world than to any other aspect as it occurs and reoccurs in physical and natural sciences (Kwak, 2010). It is referred to as the language used to describe the problems arising from most branches of science and technology. It is however, found basically in almost all aspects of discipline, most especially in areas such as quantity, structure and space. The interrelationship existing between mathematics and advancement of the human race shows the importance of mathematics in human life.

Mathematics as a field of study over the years has been regarded as a worrisome subject as statistics have shown that the percentage of students' performance in it in public Examination such as WAEC and NECO has been low and one of the identifiable reasons recently offered by the WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2018) is that students find it difficult to translate word problems to equations. The WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2021) further affirmed students' poor interpretation of questions (both word and non-word problems) and inability to apply mathematical principles correctly. Numerous reasons have been given for the poor performance of students among which are, the use of non-appropriate teaching methods, lack of frequent interaction between teacher-students, students-students, the school environment, not using instructional materials and lack of interest in the subject.

Interest of students have been considered as an important factor in the teaching of mathematics. According to Arthur (2019), interest as one of the constructs is shadowed by the search of students' performance in mathematics and that students who develop interest in mathematics finds it easy to perform in the subject. The development of any nation lies in her dexterity for strategies that can arouse the interest of the students to love and embrace mathematics, science and technology (Ado, 2018). The strategies for arousing students' interest could also be achieved through the use of instructional materials.

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Instructional materials have been considered very important in the teaching of mathematics. A well-planned and imaginative use of visual aids in mathematics lessons do much to banish apathy, supplement of inadequacy of books as well as arouse the interest of students. The use visual instructional aid makes the lesson practical such that it enables students to see the links between concepts, thereby helping the flow of thought which assist in their logically thinking. Visual instructional aides (pictures, post cards, graph, diagrams, charts, maps, film strip and models) are very crucial to the teaching of mathematics. Many teachers over the years have endeavoured to select instructional materials that relates to the content of mathematics subject, in order to facilitate in-depth understanding of such mathematics lessons, and to make learning of mathematics interesting and attractive to the learner. Different strategies such as the audio, visual, and audio-visual teaching materials have been developed and used in the teaching of mathematics overtime, yet, records still show a significant increase in the poor performance of students in mathematics examinations (Levesque, Stanck and Ryan 2004). It is in the light of this that the research work seeks to address the issue of students' poor performance in the subject by introducing internet application tools such as slack and WhatsApp as a teaching resource to help improve students' performance in mathematics examinations.

Social media could be described as internet application tools which provides an opportunity for users to converse and interact in sharing of text and multimedia contents via virtual networks. According to Joseph (2013) and Nottle (2010), social networking help in schools and universities to leverage and complement formal education activities and enhance learning outcome. It also provides opportunities for new learning relationship as well as strengthening teaching and learning process. Joseph (2013) further reiterated that teaching-learning and adapting to the world using a relatively new form of communication is made easy through social media. This is why social media tools such as slack and WhatsApp is intended by this work to see if the performance of students can be enhanced.

WhatsApp is a mobile application that allows users to communicate with one another using a smartphone or a computer (Edglossary, 2016 cited in Bruno & Layer, 2020)). It helps in providing instructions when the instructor and students are separated by distance, time or both. Teachers can use WhatsApp to communicate with their students more swiftly and effectively. Group chat features can be used to coordinate learning and studies within and outside the school premises to produce lessons that could be listened to at students' leisure, and maintain constant contact with students outside of the classroom. Bruno and Layer (2020) investigated the effects of WhatsApp Use on Students' Socio-Emotional Development and Academic Achievement and found that video chatting, online chatting through WhatsApp and frequent use of WhatsApp has effect on students' socio-emotional development and academic achievement. Folasayo and Olajide (2022) examined effects of WhatsApp group learning platform on senior secondary schools' students' learning outcomes in Science, Technology, and Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria and found that there was no significant difference between the performances mean scores of students exposed to STM through the WhatsApp Group Learning Platform and those exposed to the conventional method

Slack is a Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) tool widely used as a collaborative tool in institutions. It is an application that can support the teacher in giving the material and assignment, and can improve their teaching practices (Perkel 2017; Heryandi, 2020). Teckchandani (2018) argues that it can also be used effectively in the classroom, as students will often find their own way of communicating with each other around an assessment which normally includes a combination of texting, email, and cloud-based services. According to Muller (2023), Slack allows for setting up channels dealing with different aspects, for instance, readings, lectures, or assignments. Transparency enhances fairness since students who are less willing to ask questions will be able to read the responses. Instructors can encourage students to help each other before providing an answer and share additional materials without drafting a formal email. Learners can communicate with one another and approve content by adding emojis below messages. Meenakshi (2013) investigated importance of ICT in education and found that teacher's empowering and significant achievement in teaching and learning can be improved by the use of the online application, such as Slack application in classroom practices.

The overwhelming adoption of these applications can be linked to the fact that the students have tremendously embraced the use of mobile devices as an integral part of their everyday life. In regard to WhatsApp becoming a growing phenomenon in academic usage for discussing academic topics of mutual interest and Slack being an application that can provide collaboration and communication issues. This study sought to examine the influence of social Networking such as Slack and WhatsApp in the teaching and learning of Mathematics in secondary school in Yenagoa metropolis of Bayelsa State.

Students' mathematics performance has been poor over the years. This poor performance of student in tests and examinations has been a challenge to the schools, educators, and the teachers. Hence, different methods and resources have been adopted in the teaching of mathematics which included, discovery method, traditional method as well as the problem-solving method to see if it could help to improve students' performance in mathematics. These methods and resources have not completely worked out in the enhancement of the performance of students in Mathematics. it is on this note that the study seeks

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to ascertain if social networking tools (WhatsApp and Slack) are used in the teaching of mathematics would enhance students' performance in mathematics.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the impact of social network applications on interest and performance in concept quadratic equation among secondary students in Yenagoa metropolis. Specifically, the study sort to

1. Determine the difference in the mean interest score of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and that taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.
2. Determine the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.

Research Questions

The following Research Questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis?
2. What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was quasi-experimental design, specifically, the pretest-posttest control group design. This design was used because the students were left in their intact classes to avoid disruption of classes. The population of the study consisted of a total of two thousand, two hundred and three (2,203) students in senior secondary two (SS II) 2022/2023 academic session in the thirteen public secondary schools in Yenagoa metropolis of Bayelsa State. The sample comprised of one hundred and fifty (151) students in senior secondary two (SS II) drawn from three schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area. The sample was selected purposely because the researchers ensured that the students in the selected intact classes for the experimental group had either their own computer, phone or can use that of their parents. The problem-solving method was used as the background teaching method for all the three groups. The experimental groups, one was taught using Slack and the other WhatsApp.

The instruments used for the study were the Mathematics Interest Inventory (MII) and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). MII had 10 items on mathematics interest with four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD); while MAT had twenty (20) multiple item questions with four (4) options in each question. The test questions were set on Quadratic Equation. The instrument had two sections, sections A and B. Section A contained students' information such as number, gender, class and test instructions while section B contained the twenty (20) multiple item questions on mathematics. One (1) mark was awarded for each correct option chosen by students while an incorrect option attracted a score of zero (0). The test was based on a maximum score of twenty (20) and a minimum score of one (0).

The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was validated by two secondary school teachers of ten years teaching experience and one lecturer from the department of science Education in Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Inland. These experts made the necessary corrections which were incorporated in the final copy of the instrument. The instrument Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was trail-tested to establish its reliability with twenty (20) Mathematics students who were from the population of the study but not part of the sampled schools. The data was collated and analyzed using Kuder-Richardson formula-20, which yielded the reliability coefficient of 0.87

Permission was obtained from principals of the selected school to carry out the research. Students in the first school were taught using problem solving strategy only while students in the other two schools were taught using Slack and WhatsApp social networking tools as teaching resources with problem solving as the base teaching method. The tools were used to transfer materials, assignments and as discussion groups among students during or after class periods.

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The three group of students from the three selected schools were taught for the period of two weeks as prescribed by the scheme of work. After the teaching and learning process, the students were administered with Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The test scripts were collected, marked and scored. Data collected from the students were analyzed using adjusted mean, standard deviation and ANCOVA test statistics. All hypothesis were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without?

Table 1: Adjusted Mean Interest Scores and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and without Resource

Resources	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
Slack App	44	25.12	3.90
WhatsApp	43	24.46	4.91
Without App	44	21.78	6.64

Table 1, shows that the mean interest scores of students taught using Slack App is 25.12. WhatsApp is 24.46 and those taught without is 21.78. The results indicates that Students taught using Slack had the highest mean interest score, followed by WhatsApp and students taught without resource had the least.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.

Table 3: ANCOVA Analysis of Interest Scores of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and those taught without Resource

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	f	P-value
Covariates	Pre-Interest	973.31	1	973.31	46.64	.00
Main Effects	App Tools	274.97	2	137.49	6.59	.00
Residual		2650.30	127	20.87		
Total		3898.58	130	29.99		

Table 3 shows that the calculated probability value (P-value) of App Tools is .00 which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there exists significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught Using lecture method in yenagoa metropolis.

Table 4: LSD Post hoc Pairwise Comparison Test of Students' Post-Interest Scores Classified by Instructional Resources with Pre-Interest Scores as Covariate

(I) App Tools	(J) App Tools	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. at P < .05
Slack App	WhatsApp	0.66	.99	.50
	Without App	3.34*	.98	.00
WhatsApp	Slack App	-0.66	.99	.50
	Without App	2.68*	.98	.01
Without App	Slack App	-3.34*	.98	.00
	WhatsApp	-2.68*	.98	.01

* = significant at .05 alpha level.

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As shown in table 4, the mean difference of students taught using Slack and WhatsApp is 0.66, Slack and without app is 3.34 while WhatsApp and without app is 2.68. This indicates that Slack App is the most effective in facilitating- students' interest on the mathematics concept they were taught during this research work, followed by WhatsApp while without app is the least. The table reveal a significant mean difference between Slack and without app, and WhatsApp and without app at .05 level of significance.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without?

Table 2: Adjusted Mean Performance Scores and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and without Resource

Resources	N	Adjusted Mean	SD
Slack App	44	18.93	3.22
WhatsApp	43	17.88	3.60
Without App	44	15.69	4.41

Table 2, shows that the mean performance scores of students taught using Slack App is 18.93. WhatsApp is 17.88 and those taught without is 15.69. The results indicates that Students taught using Slack had the highest mean performance score, followed by WhatsApp and students taught without resource had the least.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught using lecture method in Yenagoa metropolis.

Table 5: ANCOVA Analysis of Performance Scores of Students Taught Quadratic Equations Using Slack, WhatsApp and without Resource

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	f	P-value
Covariates	Pre-test	13.43	1	13.43	0.93	.34
Main Effects	App Tools	228.63	2	114.31	7.95	.00
Residual		1826.69	127	14.38		
Total		2068.75	130	15.91		

Table 5 shows that the calculated probability value (P-value) of App Tools is .00 which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there exists significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using social media (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught Using lecture method in yenogoa metropolis. In order to ascertain the direction of significance the scores are further subjected to the post hoc analysis as shown in table 6.

Table 6: LSD post hoc Pairwise Comparison Test of Students' Post-Interest Scores Classified by Instructional Resources with Pre-Interest Scores as Covariate

(I) App Tools	(J) App Tools	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign at P < .05
Slack App	WhatsApp	1.05	.82	.20
	Without App	3.24*	.82	.00
WhatsApp	Slack App	-1.05	.82	.20
	Without App	2.19*	.85	.01
Without App	Slack App	-3.24*	.82	.00
	WhatsApp	-2.19*	.85	.01

* = significant at .05 alpha level.

As shown in table 6, the mean difference in the performance of students taught using Slack and WhatsApp is 1.05, Slack and without app is 3.24 while WhatsApp and without app is 2.19. This indicates that Slack App is the most effective in facilitating- students' interest on the mathematics concept they were taught during this research work, followed by WhatsApp

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while without app is the least. The table revealed a significant mean difference between Slack and without app, and WhatsApp and without app at .05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on the mean interest scores of students taught quadratic equations using internet tools (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without indicated a significant difference. Students taught using Slack and WhatsApp performed significantly better than those taught without app. The finding may have resulted to easy access to facilities and services as well as distant exchanges and collaboration. The tools may have been user-friendly, and promote users' interaction with fellow students and teachers. Instantaneous interactions provision of the tools for answering of question may have generated the interest of students. The study is in line with Bruno and Layer (2020), who investigated the effects of WhatsApp Use on Students' Socio-Emotional Development and Academic Achievement and found that video chatting, online chatting through WhatsApp and frequent use of WhatsApp has effect on students' socio-emotional development and academic achievement. Bruno and Layer (2020) state that the socio-emotional development of students being aroused would make the students become interested in whatever may have resulted to that enhancement. The study also agrees with the statement of Teckchandani (2018), who argued that Slack can be used effectively in the classroom, as students will often find their own way of communicating with each other around an assessment which normally includes a combination of texting, email, and cloud-based services.

The findings on the mean performance scores of students taught quadratic equations using internet tools (Slack and WhatsApp) and those taught without indicated a significant difference. The findings reveal that students taught using Slack and WhatsApp performed significantly better than those taught without app. The apps been able to provide students with a lot of collaboration with peers through direct messages and channels may have given the students the opportunity of sharing ideas thereby enhancing their performance. The collaboration which provided students with the opportunity of interaction may have stimulated the ability of different thinking by asking or sharing knowledge in their groups thereby reaching new way of thinking and understanding. The findings of the study are in line with that of Folasayo and Olajide (2022), who examined effects of WhatsApp group learning platform on senior secondary schools' students' learning outcomes in Science, Technology, and Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria and found that there was no significant difference between the performances of mean scores of students exposed to STM through the WhatsApp Group Learning Platform and those exposed to the conventional method

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that Slack and WhatsApp applications significantly aroused students' interest and achievement. The applications effectively brought students far and near through its application in their interactions thereby facilitating the process of teaching and learning of mathematics. The applications also demonstrated the increased flexibility of education that can be promoted through online application where learners would have the potential to access new knowledge and new experience.

Recommendations

1. Internet application tools should be used as teaching resource in the secondary school system by teachers to enable the students interact and improve their logical reasoning on the various mathematics topics.
2. Students using social networking tool for learning mathematics should be appropriately monitored and guided on the proper ways of applying social networking as a learning tool for the purpose of improving upon their academic performance.
3. The government should organize seminars and workshops to educate and inform parent and guardians on the need to purchase a type of phone that can facilitate the use of the internet in order to enhance effective learning of mathematics via the internet.
4. Teachers should endeavour to distribute mathematics assignment through social networking tool (Slack and WhatsApp) to all students after applying problem solving teaching strategy in the classroom.

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